

FROM THE HISTORY OF CHORAL PERFORMANCE

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Abstract. This article talks about the history of choral performance, music theory and the classification of conductors.

Key words: music, art, choral performance, sound, community, creativity.

ИЗ ИСТОРИИ ХОРОВОГО ИСПОЛНИТЕЛЬСТВА

Аннотация. В статье говорится об истории хорового исполнительства, теории музыки и классификации дирижеров.

Ключевые слова: музыка, искусство, хоровое исполнительство, звук, сообщество, творчество.

It is known that music means "the art of the muses" in Greek¹. Music is a form of art that reflects a person's emotional experiences, thoughts, imagination through musical sound - tone, consistency or set of melodies. Its content consists of changing musical-artistic images, and it embodies various human moods - elation, joy, pleasure, sadness, danger, fear and a number of other emotions. In addition, music vividly reflects the will qualities of a person, such as determination, aspiration, thoughtfulness, restraint, and his nature - his client. Volitional and pictorial possibilities of music were highly evaluated, commented and scientifically researched by Greek scientists - Pythagoras, Plato, Aristotle, Eastern thinkers - Farabi, ibn Sina, Jami, Navai, Babur, Kavkabi, figures of Sufism - Imam Ghazali, Kalabadi Bukhari. In ancient Europe, more precisely, in a small village church in Italy, there lived a person named Guido de Arezzo (Guido of Aretino, about 990-1050), a choirmaster and music theorist. In order to explain to children, he used five fingers on the hand (now the name of this system is called "Solmization") to show the location of the pitches, to sing high or low.

It is said that musical notation is formed in this way. Choir is a group of singers, derived from the Greek word "Horos", meaning a group of singers gathered under one goal and task. From small folk songs to large choral works, singing according to the abilities of one's voice is called a choir. Choir performance is a mass democratic art that involves complex work. It educates the musical-aesthetic taste of performers and listeners. The word "conductor" is derived from the French language and means "conductor". Of course, when singing in a group or performing a melody in a group on musical instruments, the sound of the conductor is important.

When it comes to the classification of a conductor, there are orchestra conductors and choral conductors. Although these two professions are related by the word management, their duties are different. For example, if an orchestra conductor sets the musical direction, dynamics, lines and other similar requirements of the work as a goal, the choir conductor, in addition to the requirements set by the orchestra conductor, will have breath, speech, pronunciation, the beginning of a sentence, focuses on connection, flow and completion. In the process of working with the choir, it is necessary to pay attention to the control of the rest of the voice. Because if a person uses his voice without stopping for 10-15 minutes and this situation is repeated continuously,

negative changes may occur in the sound fibers in the throat. Besides, the conductor of the choir must be able to sing beautifully.

Because, during the work process, it is necessary to sing to the choir. The conductor of the choir must strictly comply with the above requirements. In the book "Uzbekistan Children's Choir Culture" (Tashkent 2002) by N.A. Bakhritdinova, professor of the Department of Choral Conducting of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, there is more about the choir, along with how to work with the choir, choral culture, choral art, history, and methods of working with the choir in Uzbekistan and the world. It is possible to have a lot of information. It is known from history that sounds existed even before the creation of mankind. After the creation of mankind, various creatures, birds, animals, and natural phenomena tried to express their voices. Later, when they started to live as a group and a tribe, they were able to shout as a group and scare them with different sounds in order to avoid the attack of animals. In addition, when danger is felt, they warn each other using different voices. The culture, national art and rich artistic traditions of each nation are determined by material and spiritual wealth inherited from ancestors. One of such values is the art of singing. Music originated with sound. For centuries, thousands of years, the art of sound existed even before musical instruments were created. After that, musical instruments were invented. With songs and melodies, a person can be brought to a state of goodness, light, purity, cheerfulness, and other mental states in any situation. Ancient scientists have emphasized that even mental illness can be treated with music.

This period is famous for the emergence of ancient oral musical-poetic creativity, dominated by ethnic mythological heroism. Heroic legends, epic songs are full of creative images of the valiant struggle of the peoples of Central Asia for their independence, who sacrificed his life for the sake of the freedom of his people - the incomparable bravery of Shiroq and his attitude to the Motherland. fragments have survived to us. For example: Rustam and his battles, the supposed love of the princess, the system of legends about Rustam and Siyovush and other famous people are among them. Avesta hymns are performed in recitative style.

Hymns were sung and danced around the sacred fire. People's holiday ceremonies, for example, in spring, Navrozi in the world, labor ceremonies. Educating the young generation in the spirit of universal and national talents, promoting music culture in a wide scope, in developing the aesthetic taste and spiritual perfection of the young generation, confidence, kindness, honesty, patience, justice, occupying the heights of enlightenment. to learn, to inculcate in the minds of every young person is the highest goal of our pedagogy. The peoples of Central Asia also enjoyed the art of choral performance due to the need of the times and the convergence of cultures.

Although they do not have their own professional choral culture that has been preserved historically, they have age-old songs and musical heritage that are closely related to collective singing, people's lifestyle, life, labor activity.

In the second half of the 19th century, societies of music lovers started their activities.

Among such societies, the choir society called "Lira" was founded by Kapellmeister V. Leysek, and the local people were interested in a new form of art. Under the influence of the activities of this society, changes occurred in living conditions and lifestyle. Interest in world culture was growing. At concerts organized by V. Leisek, choruses from the operas of world-

renowned composers - Meyerbeer, J. Verdi, M. Glinka and A. Dargomijsky were performed for the first time and left a great impression on the audience.

It is known to everyone that many examples of ancient musical folklore have been studied by our scholars before. The samples of creativity were mostly related to certain days of the year, i.e. rituals. The creativity of the Uzbek people can be cited as an example. "Tulip holiday", labor songs - "Khashar", "Pakhta teradi", "Sus xotin", wedding ceremony songs - "Yor-yor", "O'1ap", performed by children - "Boychechak", "Songs of Ramadan", "The stork has arrived", "The sun has risen", "Chori chamber" and similar songs can be sung in the form of a choir performance.

They were performed spontaneously only in the heart of nature, in specific ceremonies.

After the performance of the choir moves to the stage conditions, the leader should lead it.

The process of singing as a group in various forms has caused the emergence of certain genres in Uzbek folklore. As the first stage of choral art, it is possible to consider the emergence of the yalla genre, combining song and dance. The main text of the song is performed by the yallachi together with the dance, and the chorus is accompanied by a small group of singers, although in one voice. Also, performing as a team can be seen in dervish dances. Men's zikr is a clear example of this.

Songs from the vocal parts of "Shashmaqom", an ancient heritage collected over the centuries, were also performed by the ensemble of singers. In particular, collective singing of Uzbek folk songs and statuses became a great ground for the development of choral art among the peoples of Central Asia in the future. P. Chesnokov is one of the founders of the choir conductor.

His book "The Choir and its Management" (1940) contributed to the formation of the science of choral studies. P.P. Levando wrote a book (1974) about "Some problems of the science of choral studies" and in this book the problems related to choral studies were solved in every way. Uzbek choir conductors R.Khubralov, Ye.Gudkova, A.Vasileva, B.Umedjonov, A.Vokhidov, M.Subaeva, Sh.Yormatov, N.I.Kaziev, M.Azimov, A.Khamidov, B.Lutfullaevlar, L. Dzhumaeva, D. Malikova, D. Zhdanov, Yu. Khusnutdinova, Sh. Boboxonova, I. Matyakubov and others have been contributing to the development of the choral culture of Uzbekistan with their pedagogical and performing activities.

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